

Kneeing ability of promising submergence-tolerant rice lines

A. S. Rao, P. S. S. Murthy, D. R. Rao, N. S. Reddy, and K. R. K. Murthy, Agricultural Research Station, Pulla 534401, West Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh, India

Kneeing ability is an important characteristic of rices grown in deepwater areas. We evaluated 11 promising submergence-tolerant lines and check variety CN540 for kneeing ability and yield performance in 1989 wet season.

Kneeing ability and grain yield of deepwater rice lines under 40-cm water. Pulla, West Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh, India, 1989.

Variety	Kneeing ability (score) ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		With 40-cm water	With 80-cm water
PLA7007	1	3.0	2.1
PLA7044	1	1.9	0.8
PLA8574	1	3.2	2.2
PLA8575	1	2.5	1.1
PLA7020	3	2.7	1.4
PLA7111	3	1.9	0.6
PLA7121	3	3.3	1.9
CN540	3	2.5	0.8
PLA7051	5	2.5	0.9
PLA7052	5	2.3	0.7
PLA7056	5	4.1	1.8
PLA7112	5	2.7	1.5
LSD (0.05)		0.6	0.2

^a Standard evaluation system for rice.

Seeds were sown 11 Jun and seedlings transplanted 10 Jul. Water depth was maintained at about 2 cm. At 30 d after transplanting (DT), three plants/variety were pulled without damaging the root and placed horizontally on the soil. Kneeing ability was scored 8 d later. PLA7007, PLA7044, PLA8574, and PLA8575 scored 1 for kneeing ability (see table).

Water depth was increased to 80 cm from 40 DT. Yields were high only in PLA8574 and PLA7007; both had high scores for kneeing ability. □

Grain quality

Element content characteristics of 51 good quality brown rices

Qiu Lingcang, Pan Jun, and Duan Binwu, China National Rice Research Institute (CNRRI), Hangzhou 310006, China

We studied the content of 41 element characteristics of 51 good quality brown rices with high nutritional, cooking, or eating quality.

Seed from the CNRRI Rice Germplasm and Resource Department was sown in 1988. After threshing and dehulling, the brown rice was ground, mixed, and wet-digested with HNO₃-HClO₄. The digests were analyzed by inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectrometry using suitable reference standards.

Among the 41 elements, P was highest, and Sc lowest (see figure).

When we compared the contents of 15 elements of quality rice grown on the CNRRI farm with those of conventional brown rice from the Taihu River valley, the order queues were similar:

CNRRI farm:

P>K>Mg>Ca>Mn>Zn>Fe>Na>Al>Cu>Ni>Mo>V>Cr>Co

Taihu River:

P>K>Mg>Na>Ca>Mn>Zn>Al>Fe>Cu>Ni>Mo>V>Cr>Co

Results of *u* test indicate significantly higher (P<0.01) P, K, Mg, Ca, Zn, Fe, Mo,

Element contents of 51 brown rices.

Ni, Cr, and Co, but significantly lower Al, Na, and V for good quality rice than for conventional rice.

The average coefficient of variation (CV) of 41 elements is 67.6 ± 49.2%. □

Grain quality of some red rice genotypes

N. R. Bai, A. Regina, R. Devika, S. Leenakumari, D. S. R. Devi, and C. A. Joseph, Rice Research Station, Moncompu, India

The qualities of various red rice genotypes grown in different crops at Moncompu were determined at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India. Aruna showed minimum values for the hulling and milling percentages; Karthika expressed the maximum (see table).

Grain quality attributes of 11 red rice genotypes. Kerala, India, 1989.

Genotype	Brown rice			Milled rice						
	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	L/B ratio	Hulling percentage (% of rough rice)	Milling percentage (% of rough rice)	Alkali spreading value	Water uptake (%)	Amylose content (% dry basis)	Protein content (% dry basis)	Elongation ratio
Bhadra	5.11	2.42	2.11	79.5	73.5	7.0	350	21.1	10.2	1.76
Asha(R)	6.20	2.58	2.40	80.0	73.5	6.0	365	18.9	9.4	1.61
Pavizham	5.32	2.72	1.95	79.5	73.5	3.0	315	16.0	7.5	1.69
Karthika	7.05	2.50	2.82	80.5	74.5	6.0	355	21.2	10.6	1.53
Aruna	5.39	2.55	2.11	74.0	64.5	3.0	240	20.6	9.6	2.23
Makam	5.33	2.31	2.39	79.0	70.0	6.0	260	18.6	9.4	1.62
Remya	6.56	2.60	2.52	75.5	70.0	6.0	320	21.9	10.9	1.92
Kanakam	5.38	2.53	2.13	76.5	68.5	2.0	230	20.6	9.5	1.75
KAU200	5.35	2.54	2.11	79.5	70.5	5.3	320	20.3	9.2	1.79
KAU204	5.32	2.46	2.16	75.0	67.5	5.0	325	20.3	9.4	1.84
KAU168	5.74	2.22	2.58	74.5	67.0	3.0	230	19.4	9.2	1.81

Grain length was 5.11-7.05 mm and length/breadth ratio was 1.95 to 2.82. Water uptake was highest in Asha (R), and lowest in Kanakam and KAU168. Amylose content ranged from 16% in Pavizham to 21.9% in Remya.

Protein content was highest in Remya (10.9% dry basis) and lowest in Pavizham (7.5%). Elongation ratio ranged from 1.53 in Karthika to 2.23 in Aruna. □

an effective, quick way to transfer the resistance gene and obtain stable pollen progenies with BB resistance.

Of 579 H₂ pollen strains of seven combinations, 572 strains (95.5%) were uniform and stable, 62.9% with high or moderate resistance and 32.7% with no resistance. Additionally, 27 heterozygous strains (4.5%) showed segregating resistance (see figure).

The BB resistance of H₂ plants is more significant than that of F₂ plants. For example, in the progenies of Shennong 1033/75-34, lesion area variation is 5-100% in H₂ and 5-45% in F₂. Growth duration and resistance show a significant relationship. BB resistance is higher in strains with longer growth duration.

H₂ strains varied greatly in growth duration, plant height, panicle length, and grain weight. Genetic analysis of results indicated that in the combination, a dominant epistatic gene controlled BB resistance. Broad heritability was more

Pest resistance—diseases

Genetic analysis of bacterial blight (BB) resistance in rice anther culture progenies

Zhang Chengmei, Lu Jiaan, and Zhang Zhenhua, *Crop Breeding and Cultivation Research Institute (CBCRI), Shanghai Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Shanghai 201106*; and Zhang Qi, *CBCRI, Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Beijing, China*

To study BB resistance inheritance in rice anther culture progenies, we crossed susceptible Shennong 1033 (japonica) with resistant varieties: indicas Zenith, 75-35, IR20; and japonicas Wase Aikoku 3, Pei Zhao 15, Bang Zhu Mang, Java 14. F₁ plants of the combinations were used for anther culture. BB resistance was evaluated by the IRRI standard system.

We observed the transfer of the resistance gene in pollen plants (H₂) and resistance stability in H₂, H₃, and H₄. results indicated that anther culture was

BB resistance reaction of anther culture H₂ populations derived from 7 combinations.